

HIGH RATE OF SCHOOL FEES IN PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN NIGERIA: IMPLICATION TO EDUCATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The paper examines the cause and effect of high rate of school fees in private schools in Nigeria. Some of the major causes of high rate of school fees include; high tax rate, ample resources and development of todays and tomorrows world. The various forms of fees charges in private school include; tuition fee, development fee, vocational fee among others. The paper also analyses some of the negative effects of high rate of school fees in the society such as widening the gap between children of the rich and poor in Nigeria. The paper therefore suggests that government should exempt private schools from most taxes till the achievement of a 100% literacy rate in the country. The paper in the final analysis recommends that the only solution to the problem of high rate of school fees among private schools is that government at all levels should make public school education system more effective in such a way that no parent would prefer sending his/her child to private school over public school in the country.

Keywords: High rate, School fees, Private School, Causes, Forms, Effect.

Introduction

Education in Nigeria is becoming something that is reserved only for the

rich. Private schools in Nigeria charge fees exorbitantly and the frequently upward review of these fees are beyond the reach of many average Nigerians.

The fees charged by private schools range between ₦620,000 and ₦3,000,000 (Nigerian University Scholarship, 2014). With the declining academic activities of public institution in Nigeria coupled with low or inadequate carrying capacity, many parents who could have taken solace in private schools are inhibited due to huge cost. It is obvious with the judging by the fees they charge that private universities according to Nigerian University Scholarship (2014) can only accommodate the children of the affluent except, of course, those of middle class parents that are willing to struggle and sacrifice other comforts of life. The incidence of the burden of these huge fees parents pay is obvious on the standard of living of many families.

Private owners of schools in Nigeria should give this a re-think to encourage more patronage especially as there is sense in economics of large scale production. Student Nigeria (2014) and Brimtime (2014), reported the fees charged by some secondary school in Nigeria to range between one million and four million naira (₦1,000,000 and ₦4,000,000) annually. This we think does not really make sense. It is simply a display of affluence. The amount paid by one student in these schools can be used toward scholarship for an entire secondary school in a local government. (Brimtime: 2014).

School fees refer to the money one must pay for an educational program. Manga (2015), defined school fees as source of

finance that comes from charging school fees on every child who attends school. Some money is charged for tuition fees; registration fees, examination fees, laboratory fees, development fees, enrolment fees, vocational fees, PTA fees, accommodation fees and feeding fees. School fees constitute an important source of finance in private educational institution. Peretomode (2004), viewed school fees as what is paid in some state at the secondary and tertiary institutions. Other fees such as lodging and feeding fees are also paid. These represent considerable private contribution to education finance in the country. According to US Legal (2016), private schools are also known as independent schools. They are not administered by local, state or federal governments. They have the right to select their students and are funded in whole or in part by charging their students tuition. They do not rely on government funding. Students can get scholarship into private schools. This make the cost cheaper depending on the talent the students have. These schools attempt to provide a level of education equal to or better than that available in public schools.

With regard to high rate of school fees in private school in Nigeria, it is the students that bear the burden of this increment wherever the private management increased the school fees almost after one or two years (Okeye 2013). The fundamental questions that this paper sets to answer therefore are; what are the causes of high rate of school

fess in private school? What are the different forms of high rate of school fess in private school? What are the effects of this high rate of school fees in private school? What is the reason of parents for sending their children to private schools?

Review of Empirical Studies

In a study conducted by Sunday and Gomiluk (2014) to test the relationship between the component of education costs and the demand for private secondary education in Akwa Ibom state; six hundred students and thirty principals were drawn through proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Data collection was through structured questionnaire. The findings showed that there was a statistically significant relationship between education cost and the demand for private secondary education in Akwa Ibom. What differentiate the study with the present one is that the former is on education costs and demand for private school while the latter is based on high rate of school fees in private school.

Jacob (2015) conducted a study on private participation in education in Nigeria taking Kogi State as a case study. The study sampled three hundred school principals. The study finds out that there are high school fees, creating unhealthy social class among students. The difference between this study and present one is that the above study is on private participation in education while the present one is on high rate of school fees in private school in Nigeria.

A study was conducted by Okoli (2015) on impact of fees increase on university students education in Nigeria. Five hundred and eight university students were drawn as sample of the study. The study finds out that fees increase have damaging impact on both students and their programs. The steady decline in the amount of money ploughed into university by government has given rise to steady decline in the quality of education and fees increase is driven by this decline. What differentiate Okoli's study with the present one is that the former investigated on impact of fees increase on university alone while the latter concentrates on high rate of school fees in all the level of education.

Causes of High Rate of School Fees

According to Edugrid (2019), there are a number of reasons for this drastic increase in school fees and this paper tried to shed light on a few of its causes as follows:

1. **High Tax Rates:** Private schools are treated as fully commercial entities by the government. They pay high income tax, heavy property taxes, school registration fee, registration visit fee, sports funds, school affiliation fee, affiliation visit fee, renewal fee of school registration, renewal fee of school affiliation, building fitness certificate fee, building hygienic certificate fee, endowment funds,

- commercial utility bills, service tax, professional tax, trade tax, building board rent tax, parking fee, sanitation fee, scouting fund, armed licenses fee, and a host of other taxes and levies. The levied taxes also increase annually, which increase the cost of installing effective security apparatus.
2. **Higher Cost of Installing Effective Security Apparatus:** Ever since the tragic terrorist attack in Borno and Yobe Schools that shock the entire nation, security measures in private schools have been treated as high priority with security costs increasing. These security costs are then covered from the student's fee.
 3. **Increase in Rental Costs:** Most private schools operate on rented premises. Rent increases per annum. Typically every three to five years, lease agreements are renewed, at which point landlord aggressively renegotiate lease terms. Landlords are aware that schools have limited options because their cost of relocation is very high.
 4. **High Cost of Wages:** Private schools often have to hire staff with higher level of expertise, in order to maintain the quality of education they provide. This combined with the revision of teachers' salaries, on average
- minimum wages per year, promotion, years of experience, are also a reason for the hike in school fees.
5. **Poor Quality of Education at Public Schools:** Failure of the state to impart education through public schools has also given impetus to private individuals to fill this vacuum. Owing to this monopolistic market, parents really do not have much of a choice, and they are obliged into paying whatever fee the schools demand.
 6. **Money Making Motives:** Most private schools exist with the sole purpose of making profits. While the focus of an education institute should be to maintain good, long term relations with the students and parents, and provide premium education at break-even, it is unfortunately rarely the case in Nigeria. Private schools claim that their business method is based on the open market principle of you get what you pay for. Therefore, any additional service provided, no matter how small is accounted and charged for.
 7. **Elite Target Market:** Most niche private schools want their schools to be known as exclusive educational institutions, and hence, charge very high fee for premium services. Most private schools in Nigeria seem to be following this

trend and charge higher fee so that society views these schools as premium and better quality.

8. **High Utility and Operational Expenses:** Average electricity expenses across Nigeria. Private schools pay the commercial tariff, which is the highest tariff category. They also pay an additional security cost, computer equipment, laboratory equipment, school furniture, vehicles among others. In such circumstances, it is hardly possible for private schools not to increase the annual fee of students' registration.

Various Forms of School Fees in Private School in Nigeria

The most controversial as regards private school fees till date is the amount students pay as schools fees and registration. While some will argue that these fees are worth it based on the level of education and general life in and around the schools, some still believe the fees are outrageous and should be reduced. Here, the paper gives a detailed list of how much top private universities pay in Nigeria as tuition and accommodation charges. The paper also takes a look at other fees they charge

According to Nigerian Price (2019), the following are private universities in Nigeria and their school fees:

1. American University of Nigeria, Yola School Fees: So far this

university is one of the most expensive private institution in the country. The pay their school fees and other charges to Nigerian currency, the school fee is between ₦1,590,000 to 3,000,000 per session.

2. Achiever University, Owo School Fees: This is one of the new generation private universities in Nigeria. It is beginning to grow its reputation and attract students all around the country. Here is a breakdown of their institution Registration fee per session: ₦10,000, Accommodation per session: ₦450,000 to ₦80,000 (depending on the number of bed space per room) Development levy per session: ₦20,000 Vocational training fee per session (100level and 200 level): ₦20,000.
3. Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti. The list is definitely incomplete without the mention of one of the most reputable private universities in Nigeria. Here are the fees based on faculties.
Law: tuition: ₦1,000,000, other fees sum it all up to be ₦1,500,000
Medicine and surgery: tuition ₦1,250,000, other fees sum it all up to be ₦1,752,750
Other faculties. Tuition ₦690,750
4. Babcock University, Ilishan Remo. The tuition fees and other charges

range between ₦500,000 to ₦3,000,000. This variation is due to diversities in departmental charges and tuition fees per department. The university also offers two to three daily meal services and accommodation fees also vary, depending on the type and side of room.

5. Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo. Their tuition fees range from ₦507,000 to ₦500,000 depending on the faculty and their acceptance fees is ₦50,000
6. Igbinedion University, Okada. The tuition fees ranges from ₦540,000 to ₦3million. Students are responsible for their feeding. Accommodation ₦100,000. Other charges ₦110,000.
7. Crawford University, Igbesa. The school fee ranges from ₦489,000 to ₦600,000

According Ezebuoro (2018), the following are most expensive secondary school in Nigeria and their tuition fees:

1. British International School, Lagos. ₦4.48 million
 2. Grange High School, Lagos. ₦4.5 million
 3. Nigerian Turkish International College, Abuja. ₦1.6 million
 4. Norwegian International School, Port Harcourt. ₦1843750 million.
- A breakdown of their fees for new

intakes shows that ₦250,000 for enrollment fee, ₦250,000 for development fee, ₦1,843,759 for tuition; an extra ₦20,000 for PTA putting these together gives you a total of ₦2, 547,647 million naira.

5. Lead British International School, Abuja ₦1.5 million
6. Regent School Maitama Abuja ₦1.35 million per annum for senior secondary.

Negative Effect of High Rate School Fees in Private Schools in Nigeria

Jacob (2015), identifies various negative effect of high rate of school fees in private schools in Nigeria as follows:

1. There is an existing wide gap between the rich and poor in Nigeria already. Therefore, conscious effort to further widen this gap should be discouraged. But this is what most of this private educational institutions seem to promote; only children of the affluence could access it.
2. Children of low socio economic class will continue to be left behind of their counterpart as they are likely not to graduate within time frame since the public schools usually go on strikes. And what this means is that those in private school will continue to be ahead of their counterpart from low or poor socio-economic background. They are likely to graduate earlier.

3. With the poor condition of public schools, children in public school because they cannot afford the high fees in private schools will not have access to qualitative education compared to those in private school that have ample resources.
4. Some school age children cannot even go to school because of the high rate of tuition fees in private school and cannot be admitted to public schools because of competition and high demand.
5. Again in some private school, the amount of money student pay from one course to another as well as the nature and type of accommodation they get as not the same. For instance in a private university in Nigeria as reported by Nigerian University Scholarship (2014), accommodation depends on the student choice, either it is regular (7 in a room), premium (4 in a room) or classic (3 or 2 in a room). This discrimination is not healthy for the children that are being trained to be leaders tomorrow. The socio-economic status of students is not to be used as the basis for discrimination-especially in the area of hostel accommodation and the number of meals to be eaten per day.
6. Entrance exam should be passed for one to qualify to be in the school: unlike in public schools,

private school have entrance test that all learners should pass before an admission. This may demand extra charges that one had not planned for.

7. High rate of fees discourage students seeking transfer since they can demand the repeat of the student. Such instance may bring an extra budget that was not calculated before by the family.
8. However, some private schools do not have the privilege of the children with disabilities. They aim at enrolling a student who is physically fit to carry out learning process; this is to minimize the quality of work to be executed.

Positive Effects of High Rate of School Fees in Private School in Nigeria

According to Sharlyn, (2017) and Our Kids (2019), the positive effect of high rate of school fees in private schools includes the following:

1. Private schools have an edge over the government school because they work hard and their concerted efforts help the student to get good grades and students also learn basic etiquettes and ways of socialization as well. Every child gets proper attention of teachers and can ask for help from the teachers. People also prefer their children to attend private schools.

2. The teacher in private school is dedicated and professional. This is the main advantage of private schools. All the teachers are well educated and hold teaching certification. They treat all the students equally and pay attention to all the students of the class. The teachers of private schools communicate with all the students in a polite way and students also learn in a relaxed environment
3. Private schools have improved academic opportunities: There are different educational courses and programs being offered to students in private schools which help them grow and learn. There are extracurricular activities gifted programs which train students for their professional life. The students of the private schools are good at general knowledge and lead to a memorable student life or enriched academic opportunities.
4. The students of private school are confident: Every student gets equal presentation in private schools which boost their confidence and self-esteem. These students take an active part in debate competitions and other activities. Their communication skills are highly developed and they are quite expressive because of the conducive environment of private schools. Students of private schools are always encouraged by their teacher whenever they come up with innovative idea or participate in classroom activities, therefore, they have high self-esteem and are quite confident
5. Smaller class of private school are easy to handle. There are smaller class of private school and that teacher can easily handle their students, teacher make portfolio of each student that contain their scores in education and other extracurricular activities. These portfolios help students to work hard to improve their grades and compete with their class mates in a positive manner
6. Parental involvement: There are frequent parents teacher meeting in the private schools which keep parents aware of their children educational record and they also get to know the behavior of their kids in schools. The parental involvements also help teacher to formulate policies and plans for each student individually.
7. Private schools have no security issue: Parents feel safe by sending their children to private schools. They have the latest security system which ensures the safe environment of the school. People are screened properly before entering the schools. No cult clashes, no protests you won't live in fear of some cult members or students vandalizing properties in the name of protest. One of the biggest undoing of public universities is cultism, which has claimed the lives of thousands of

innocent people and cult members respectively. However, students in private universities are safe from fear of cult attack. Protests are also very violent these days in public schools with lots of properties destroyed and some lives in fact lost, unlike in a private school where there is no chance for protest or violence.

8. Ample resources: At private schools, you will find incredible resources to support student learning in the classroom, sport field, art studio, and beyond. Quality resources and extracurricular activities provide students with the opportunity to fully explore their interest and talents. In terms of superior real world experience and laboratory most private schools are not just well equipped but super equipped. One private schools especially universities easily dwarfs all public federal and state universities in laboratory equipment standard and volume or available per student.
9. Shared educational philosophy: There are innumerable approaches to educational philosophy, and finding a school that matches one's own perspective can create a positive productive academic experience for one's child. Whether you prefer the student directed learning method of Montessori, or the arts based curriculum, choosing the right private school will not only allow students to thrive in a supportive environment and build independence, but also gain

unique skills that fit their learning style.

10. Development for today's and tomorrow's world: Private schools go beyond offering the mandatory subjects required provincial curriculum, they can offer students a wide range of specializations including arts programs, athletics, mathematics, science. Private schools are responsible for producing many leaders in politics, business and society, with a history of adapting quickly to changes in technology and culture. And today, they are also sought by parents of kids with special needs such as behavior (including troubled teen behavior), learning, developmental, or physical disabilities. These schools really help you focus and think about your future, and how you want your life to be.
11. A definite graduation date: Unlike public institutions which are prone to strikes, private schools have a definite graduation date. During the strike the duration of time to spend on a program increase. Crime rate by students of government owned university also increased because they would be idle. Some of the students who attend private universities count down their graduation date and they will graduate exactly day they had previously calculated, try that in a public school, you will add another 300 days to make it work.

12. A faster syllabus: In private schools, special attention is given to every student of the school. The lecturers or teachers all have a duty to pay special attention to each and every one of the student and put them through their lacks. This way a student's flaw is easily detected and will be dealt with appropriately. However in public schools especially with the size and population it is impossible for this to happen. The schools have almost no personal relationship with the students and they are not aware of any personal psychological needs of the students.
13. Better welfare: The individual welfare of the student is catered for. The accommodation is way better than you get in hostels of public schools. Most time they have no light or water problems. The condition of their hostels and classes is way better too. Even in general course you won't see them running to catch sits because everyone gets to sit down comfortable. With the welfare learning is made a lot easier because you will be less strained.
14. Better moral training: The school is the melting point of all moral standards. There is no form of anti-moral behavior you would not find in a university. However, private schools, with their very strict enforcement of moral values, have reduced the decay in moral values by far.
15. Organized system: In private university system you get your transcript easily. In public universities the reverse is the case 40% of the time. Same pattern hold for jamb regularization, NYSC call-up and result checking. Same thing happened in secondary and primary public schools their report card will not be issued to them at the end of every term some time the hall year the result will not be given to them
16. No lecturer's threat: you hardly see or about lecturers harassing ladies in private institution or school or hear about lecturers threatening to fail you or not allow you to graduate. Coming down to public institutions, a lecturer can make you fail for using expensive phones while he is using low class phones etc.

Suggestion

Based on the challenges examined in this paper, the following suggestions are provided as a way to regulate private institutions.

1. The government should exempt private schools from most taxes till the achievement of a 100% literacy rate in the country. Education should be the highest priority in Nigeria, yet it is being treated as the least one. If the government has proved worthless in providing high quality education to the public, then it should at least make it possible for the public to get access to high

- quality private education, by regulating private institutions, and removing the levied taxes on educational institution.
2. Government should make security measures available in both public and private schools in order to reduce insecurity problems and cost of installing security apparatus.
 3. Government should provide rental premises for private school with low rental cost, so that rental cost will not be increasing.
 4. Government should make it mandatory for the private schools to borrow some certain percentage of their teachers so as to reduce high rate of wages.
 5. Government should make learning environment of public schools attractive in order to restore the confidence of the parents in the system.
 6. Private schools know the aim of an education institute should be to maintain good, not sole purpose of making profits. They should try to care about the predicaments of Nigerian students.
 7. Reduction of school fees that is high exorbitant. This can be done through government legislation.
 8. Government should find a way of excluding private schools from commercial tariff of electricity, so that the school fees will not be increasing annually.

Conclusion

The appearance of private practitioner in education in Nigeria has helped in no small measure to launder the battered image of schools in Nigeria, but there are some issues that are really retarding or staining these good efforts and these issues need to be addressed. Government seemed not to be seriously bothered. The future of this great country is at stake as the private management does not care about the predicaments of the Nigerian students who are our leaders of tomorrow. Reducing high rate of school fees in private schools in Nigeria is very important with the growing importance and dependence of education in Nigeria.

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